
An Analysis of the Relationship between Housing Quality and Rental Value of Residential Properties in Benin City, Nigeria

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Abstract Housing goes beyond mere shelter it also includes the facilities and other building components that make living comfortably for man, which should be adequately provided. The objective of the study includes to; examine the available housing facilities in residential properties in Benin City, developing a housing quality index for Benin City, and survey rental values of residential properties in Benin City. A non-probability sampling method was used to carry out the research work. The findings of this study show that the impact of facilities on housing conditions is significant. The study also concludes that developers should ensure that all basic facilities that will attract higher values to their property should be provided. The government should make implementable policies and established housing quality standards and supervisory agencies that will be responsible for the monitoring of housing standards. The study recommends the need for property owners/developers and users to be educated on the need for the provision of basic facilities and sustainable maintenance culture.

Keywords Housing facilities, Housing quality, Rental value, Residential properties, Benin City

1. Introduction

Urban infrastructure, apart from being an indicator for measuring environmental quality, is a catalyst for political, social, and economic development as well as the backbone of any economy as all sectors need it to effectively function. It is a physical framework of facilities through which goods and services are provided to the public [1]. This sector covers a wide range of services such as telecommunication, sewage disposal, roads, energy, water supply, agricultural, medical, educational, and other facilities, etc. Most of these services have a direct impact on man's life from his health, safety, and wellbeing. From the societal point of view, they form the bedrock of all socio-economic development in a country and are a key indicator of a nation's developmental status as well as the wellbeing of its citizens [2-3]. The basic challenges facing most African cities today apart from housing inadequacy and fluctuating property rentals are the problems of the provision and management of the few available infrastructural facilities.

The diversity of buildings, their great historical and cultural value, the uniqueness of the spatial aspect, the richness of architectural forms and details, and the trees often found there, all have a substantial influence on the quality of housing as perceived by the residents. The qualities of spatial aspect and layout, often supplemented by the specific manner in which they are used, make these areas interesting and pleasant, as well as places of attraction for many citizens of the town, and visitors from afar. However, since the middle of the 20th century, house owners, housing investors, and house users have struggled to identify the basic factors that influence residential property prices in the global housing market [4]. This problem has attracted a lot of interest from researchers, real estate surveyors, and other relevant stakeholders concern with housing development, investment, and management. For instance, rental values of residential properties in a particular residential

neighborhood in most cases differ significantly from rental values of similar residential properties in another residential neighborhood within the same metropolis. Similarly, rental values of similar houses within the same residential neighborhood also differ due to various silent reasons.

Despite the growing concern on the issues from both the foreign and local housing market, only a handful of studies in that regard have been conducted in Nigeria, with no particular study found to have statistically analyzed the combined effect of dwellings, location, and neighborhood attribute on rental values of residential properties. Most of the studies on the impact of housing attributes on house prices in the global housing market focused attention on studying the impact of individual housing attributes rather than analyzing the combined effect of the attributes on residential property prices. The most unfortunate is that no study was found in relation to the impact of housing attributes and housing prices in the current area under study, as all the related studies found in Nigeria were carried out in different geographical regions of the country other than in the area currently being examined. Thus, the impact of housing attributes (dwellings, location, and neighborhood) on the rental values of residential properties remains silent.

Residential properties transcend ordinary shelter and thus comprise of the housing facilities and other aspects of the social environment such as security and ease of movement. These properties form the basic component of residential neighborhoods in any urban centre and as such play a critical role in human development [5]. This is more the reason why their form, structure, and challenges have been of great interest to urban geographers, policymakers, and urban dwellers. The interest of the latter may however rest upon the fact that the affordability of these properties, by and large, is determined by their rental value. Several studies have however shown that residential rent tends to exhibit variation over space with housing facilities. Housing prices reflect the renter's valuation of particular sets of attributes of the property. Their findings revealed that houses with more bedrooms, living space, and generally good facilities are far more expensive than similar houses that are deficient in these attributes. Housing facilities affected rent charged on houses, there exist inequalities in the living conditions of residents across neighborhoods due to differences in availability of these facilities. I was opined that houses in the low-density areas of Jos are of greater value than those in high-density areas because of the overall quality of housing infrastructure and availability of adequate housing facilities per household size. A functional residential building is crucial to the development of a healthy and comfortable living environment. It is one of the three basic needs of man coming next in importance to food. Its importance lies not only in its value for individual households residing in it but also in the neighborhood where it is located. Just as a building is meant to be accessible, it is also meant to provide comfort for the occupier and comfort can only be obtained from the availability of adequate and appropriate facilities within and around the building. For the purpose of this study the term "housing facilities" however consist of internal facilities and the structural form of the house. Internal facilities include toilet/bathroom, kitchen, water supply, and burglary proof, among others. The structural form of a house refers to a house built with standard building materials, roofing sheets, floor and wall finishing, among others.

This study thus attempted to contribute to the knowledge base by exploring the influence of the various housing attributes on rental values of residential properties in the study area. The study examines the direct impact of dwellings, location, and neighborhood attributes on the rental values of residential properties in Benin City, Nigeria. While several studies before now have examined the effect of housing facilities on rent, very few of such have been carried out in Benin City. It is on this basis that this study investigates and analyzes residential property rent in relation to available housing facilities in different categories of neighborhoods in Benin City, Nigeria.

2. Research Methodology

2.1. Study Area

Benin City is the capital and largest city of Edo State in southern Nigeria. It is the fourth-largest city in Nigeria after Lagos, Kano, and Ibadan, with a total population of 1,782,000 as of 2021. Taub, Ben [6], it is situated approximately 40 kilometers (25 mi) north of the Benin River and 320 kilometres (200 mi) by road east of Lagos. Benin City is the centre of Nigeria's rubber industry, and oil production is also a significant industry.

2.5 Instrumentation and Data Collection

A structured questionnaire of four hundred (400) was used in order to capture data relevant to the study's objectives and research questions, three hundred and seventy (370) were retrieved. The two basic sources of data available are primary and secondary sources. Obviously, in order to achieve the objectives of this study and to broaden our knowledge, data ought to be collected, analyzed, and appraised. The primary method, as well as the secondary method of data collection, was used for this research. The data were collected from respondents with the aid of questionnaires. The form that constituted the questions of the questionnaire included those pertaining to personal information about the respondents; age, sex, marital status, educational qualifications, and years of work experience were included in the questionnaire. These were brought forward so as to enable the respondents to answer the questions posed by the problem statement adequately. Thus, it was possible to provide solutions to the questions raised by the statement of the problem. In the collection of data for the purpose of this research work, both primary and secondary sources of data collection were used.

Research instruments were the type of tools used to gather and retrieve data from the respondents. For the purpose of this study, a questionnaire was used in gathering data from the respondents for the effectiveness and accuracy of the research. The structured questionnaire was formulated to capture the analysis of the relationship between housing quality and rental value. This questionnaire has two sections; section A was focused on the demographic questions that contained variables like gender, age, level, and ministry. While section B was designed to quiz the surveyed respondents on questions pertaining to the research objectives of this research study. The structured questionnaire was designed to follow the Linkert Scale format; Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD), and Undecided (U). The questions in this instrument were derived from the research objective in this study.

3. Results

The objective of this chapter is to present, interpret and discuss the result of the analysis of the researcher survey conducted within some areas in Benin City, Edo State. The data collection instrument used for this study is a self-developed questionnaire. A total of three hundred and seventy copies of the questionnaire were administered immediately to various respondents and they were all retrieved instantly. Analysis of the background information of respondents. The sociodemographic features of the respondents such as gender, age, marital status, and educational qualification were analyzed to give information on the background information of the respondents.

3.1. Sociodemographic Features

From table 1, 43 respondents residing in the residence representing 12% were within the age bracket of 18-25 years, 180 respondents residing in the residence representing 49% were within the age bracket of 26-35 years, 86 respondents residing in the residence representing 23% were within the age bracket of 36-45 years while the remaining 61 respondents residing in the residence representing 16% were 46 years and above. Fig. 2 shows that 160 respondents residing in the residence representing 43% were males while 210 respondents residing in the residence representing 57% were females. The result in Fig.3 shows that 74 respondents residing in the residence representing 20% had no education, 56 respondents residing in the residence representing 15% had primary education, 70 respondents residing in the residence representing 19% had secondary education while the remaining 170 respondents residing in the residence representing 46% tertiary education. This implies that most of the residents are literate. The presentation of the results is similar to the work of UN_Habitat [10], Ukabam [11], Yoade *et al* [12], Yoade and Adeyemi [13], and Yust *et al.* [14].

Table 1: Age bracket of respondents

Age	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
18-25 years	43	12
26-35 years	180	49
36-45 years	86	23
46 years and above	61	16
Total	370	100

Source: Field Study, 2021

Figure 2: Sex of the respondents

Source: Field Study, 2021

3.2. Residential property

The basic types of residential properties in Benin City, Edo State are the blocks of flat residential property. The Semi-Detached flats are 2 flats combined on the same plot. It could be in a bungalow or a story building. The Detached flat is a single flat inclusively built on a site and usually a bungalow building. It is important to note that the Semi-Detached and Detached flats used are three-bedroom flats. Table 2 shows property distribution in the study area.

Table 2: Distribution of residential property types by zones

Types	Sapele Road	Ugbowo	Amagba	Airport Road	Total
Blocks of Flat	60	24	30	50	164
Semi-Detached Flat	10	37	25	20	92
Detached Flat	30	39	15	30	114
Total	100	100	70	100	370

Source: Field Study, 2021

Fig. 3: Educational background of the respondents

Figure 3: Educational background of the respondents

3.3. Housing facilities in residential zones

The housing condition components are those facilities and infrastructural whose availability in a building enhances its worth and improve the general condition of the property and the comfort of the inhabitants; these among other variables include electricity, water supply, access road, burglary proof, refuse disposal, toilet, kitchen, drainage system, wall-fence, watch day-security services and watch-night-security services, location

and other neighborhood and environmental variables. The provisions of these variables vary from area or zone to zone and from one housing unit to the other. Findings revealed that all the 370 sampled residential properties in four zones in Benin City are connected with electricity. However, water supply as presented in the table above is not based on the water supply from the public mains alone but on the provision of functional water supply either through hand-dug well or boreholes. Some residential properties are provided with good water supply sources as to where these hand-dug well and boreholes are located within the house compound influences the level of safety of such water. The collection and disposal of refuse in Benin City is not encouraging. Residential areas are not provided with any form of refuse dump or collection points. The residential properties in Sapele Road, Ugbowo, Amagba and Airport Road have private refuse collection points. The Edo State Waste Management Board and Local Health must pay more attention to this area. Toilet facility as a basic requirement for any functional residential property is lacking in some of the properties sampled. Toilet facility as used in this work means a toilet that is functional overall. Out of the 370 houses sampled only 280 houses representing have a functional toilet in these zones of Benin City (Table 3). It is necessary to note that all the residential properties in Benin City are provided with kitchen facilities. Although, few of the residential properties in Sapele road and Ugbowo still lack this facility thereby making the tenants cook their food in an unhygienic environment. The provision of wall-fence around the residential property is to guide against unwanted interruption and ensure security and safety of property in the residential buildings, hence the few residential buildings are provided with wall-fence. Landlord attitude was never considered to be a factor but location which is one of the environmental variables is a strong factor considered by all the respondents [6,8,15-16]. The housing facilities are those facilities and infrastructural whose availability in a building enhances its worth and improve the general condition of the property and the comfort of the inhabitants; these among other variables include windows (casement and slide), doors foreign security, and wooden doors), ceiling/POP/PVC, tiles (Nigerian vitrified, china and Spanish tiles). The provisions of these variables vary from area or zone to zone and from one housing unit to the other. Findings revealed that all the 370 sampled residential properties in four zones in Benin City are equipped with good windows (Table 4). It is expected that every residential property should be provided with good doors being it security or non-security doors. It is necessary to note that all the residential properties in Benin City are provided with wonderful sets of tiles. The provision of ceiling/POP/PVC was also needed and they were installed in these residential buildings.

Table 3: Available housing facilities in residential zones

Facilities	Sapele Road "Houses"	Ugbowo "Houses"	Amagba "Houses"	Airport Road "Houses"	Total
Electricity	100	100	70	100	370
Water Supply	100	100	70	100	370
Burglary Proof	100	90	65	100	355
Refuse Disposal	98	93	61	85	337
Toilet	100	100	70	100	370
Kitchen	100	100	64	100	366
Drainage System	100	85	57	100	342

Source: Field Study, 2021

Table 4: Components of Building Available in the Residential Property Studied

Components of Building	Sapele Road	Ugbowo	Amagba	Airport Road	Total
Window (Casement)	20	10	24	25	370
Window (Slider)	80	90	46	75	
Front Security Foreign Door	36	28	17	52	370
Front Security Steel Door	64	72	53	48	
Ceiling	8	47	2	5	370
POP	48	32	27	60	
PVC	44	21	41	35	
Tile (Nigerian Vitrified)	57	58	28	40	370
Tile (China)	33	42	37	52	
Tile (Spanish Tiles)	10	-	5	8	

Source: Field Study, 2021

3.4. Tenants satisfaction

The satisfaction level of tenants with the housing facilities in Benin City was examined under three groups viz; satisfied, not satisfied and indifferent. The indifference is a situation where the respondent is undecided as to the indicated grouping. The table above shows that 260 of the respondents were satisfied with the electricity supply in their buildings. This is connected with the recent transformation in the power sector in the country. This is followed by water supply, for which 300 of the respondents were satisfied with the water supply in their houses. About 130 of the respondents were not satisfied with the refuse disposal system and the condition of the drainages abutting their rented residential property. However, 350 tenants were correspondingly satisfied with the toilet, 335 of the respondents were satisfied with the burglary proof installed and 340 of the respondents were also satisfied with the kitchen provided in their residential property (Table 5). The findings have strong relationship with the studies of Kiel [17], Koutonin [7], Ilesanmi *et al.* [18], Mbachu and Lenon [19], and Morris *et al.* [20].

The satisfaction level of tenants with the condition of housing in Benin City was examined under three-group viz; satisfied, not satisfied and indifferent. The indifference is a situation where the respondent is undecided as to the indicated grouping. The table above shows that 300 of the respondents were satisfied with their fenced apartments into their buildings. This is connected with the recent transformation in the power sector in the country. This is followed by a good housing location, for which 320 of the respondents were satisfied with the location of their building. About 315 of the respondents were also satisfied with the security system. However, 343 respondents were correspondingly satisfied with the state of the building and the facilities inside (Table 6).

Table 5: Tenants Satisfaction Levels with Residential Housing Facilities

Facilities	Levels of Satisfaction			Total
	Satisfied	Not Satisfied	Indifferent	
Electricity	260	110	-	370
Water Supply	300	50	20	370
Burglary Proof	335	-	35	370
Refuse Disposal	240	130	-	370
Toilet	350	25	5	370
Kitchen	340	30	-	370
Drainage System	80	20	270	370

Source: Field Study, 2021

Table 6: Tenants Satisfaction Levels with Residential Housing Conditions

Conditions	Levels of Satisfaction			Total
	Satisfied	Not Satisfied	Indifferent	
Fenced Round	300	60	10	370
Location	320	30	20	370
Accessibility	347	13	10	370
Security	315	55	-	370
State of Building and Facilities	343	27	-	370

3.5 Effects of Facility on Rent Level

There is a relationship between the availability of facilities and level of rent. Households with both toilet and bathroom facilities are more likely to pay medium rent (35%) or high rent (almost 53%). Having both toilet and bathroom facilities tend to attract medium and high rental charges. With low rent, one gets either none of the facilities or at most one of the two facilities (7). The results seem to suggest that the availability of amenities (water and electricity supply) also has a significant effect on residential rental charges (Table 7). The results seem to suggest that the availability of amenities (water and electricity supply) also has a significant effect on residential rental charges (8). The results in Tables 9-12 show the rent value of self-contained, 2-bedroom, semi-detached, and detached apartments in the study areas.

Table 7: Availability of Facility and Rent Level

Density Response	Low Rent	%	Medium Rent	%	High Rent	%
Both Toilet and Bathroom	43	12	130	35	197	53
Only Bathroom	172	46	99	27	99	27
Only Toilet	246	66	73	20	51	14

Source: Field Study, 2021

Table 8: Effects of Availability of Amenities on Rent Level

Density Response	Low Rent	Medium Rent	High Rent	Total
Both Water and Electricity Supply	30	135	205	370

Source: Field Study, 2021

Table 9: Average Rental Value of Self-Contain Apartment in Sapele Road, Airport Road, Amagba and Ugbowo (2015-2020)

Year	Average Rental Value in Sapele Road	Average Rental Value in Ugbowo	Average Rental Value in Amagba	Average Rental Value in Airport Road
2015	₦60,000	₦40,000	₦65,000	₦65,000
2016	₦75,000	₦55,000	₦80,000	₦90,000
2017	₦90,000	₦70,000	₦95,000	₦100,000
2018	₦105,000	₦85,000	₦110,000	₦115,000
2019	₦120,000	₦97,000	₦125,000	₦130,000
2020	₦140,000	₦110,000	₦140,000	₦160,000

Source: Field Study, 2021

Table 10: Average Rental Value of Semi-Detached Flat Apartment in Sapele Road, Airport Road, Amagba and Ugbowo (2015-2020)

Year	Average Rental Value in Sapele Road	Average Rental Value in Ugbowo	Average Rental Value in Amagba	Average Rental Value in Airport Road
2015	₦200,000	₦105,000	₦210,000	₦220,000
2016	₦215,000	₦140,000	₦230,000	₦270,000
2017	₦230,000	₦160,000	₦280,000	₦310,000
2018	₦280,000	₦195,000	₦330,000	₦375,000
2019	₦350,000	₦215,000	₦380,000	₦400,000
2020	₦410,000	₦270,000	₦410,000	₦440,000

Source: Field Study, 2021

Table 11: Average Rental Value of Semi-Detached Flat Apartment in Sapele Road, Airport Road, Amagba and Ugbowo (2015-2020)

Year	Average Rental Value in Sapele Road	Average Rental Value in Ugbowo	Average Rental Value in Amagba	Average Rental Value in Airport Road
2015	₦200,000	₦105,000	₦210,000	₦220,000
2016	₦215,000	₦140,000	₦230,000	₦270,000
2017	₦230,000	₦160,000	₦280,000	₦310,000
2018	₦280,000	₦195,000	₦330,000	₦375,000
2019	₦350,000	₦215,000	₦380,000	₦400,000
2020	₦410,000	₦270,000	₦410,000	₦440,000

Source: Field Study, 2021

Table 12: Average Rental Value of Detached Flat Apartment in Sapele Road, Airport Road, Amagba and Ugbowo (2015-2020)

Year	Average Rental Value in Sapele Road	Average Rental Value in Ugbowo	Average Rental Value in Amagba	Average Rental Value in Airport Road
2015	₦210,000	₦110,000	₦225,000	₦230,000
2016	₦215,000	₦125,000	₦240,000	₦260,000
2017	₦240,000	₦160,000	₦290,000	₦320,000
2018	₦300,000	₦195,000	₦330,000	₦395,000
2019	₦370,000	₦215,000	₦400,000	₦420,000
2020	₦430,000	₦290,000	₦440,000	₦480,000

Source: Field Study, 2021

4. Discussion

The study covers a wide range of services such as sewage disposal, burglary proof, toilet, kitchen, fenced round, access roads, drainage system, water supply, and other facilities, etc. Most of these services have a direct impact on man's life from his health, safety, and wellbeing. A functional residential building is crucial to the development of a healthy and comfortable living environment. Its importance lies not only in its value for individual households residing in it but also in the neighbourhood where it is located. The housing includes the totality of the surroundings and infrastructural facilities that offer human comfort, improve the quality of human health and productivity as well as enable them to sustain their psycho-social or psycho-pathological balance in the environment where they find themselves [1, 4, 21].

Despite the growing concern on the issues from both the foreign and local housing market, only a harmful of studies in that regard have been conducted in Nigeria, with no particular study found to have statistically analyzed the combined effect of dwellings, location, and neighborhood attribute on rental values of residential properties. Most of the studies on the impact of housing attributes on house prices in the global housing market focused attention on studying the impact of individual housing attributes rather than analyzing the combined effect of the attributes on residential property prices. The findings agree with Bello *et al* [3], Chukwuma *et al.*, [23], and Dabara *et al.*, [2]. The impact of housing attributes (dwellings, location, and neighborhood) on the rental values of residential properties remains silent. The study has examined the an analysis of relationship between housing quality and rental value in Benin City It among other things revealed that, properties with better conditions in terms of infrastructures and physical soundness command higher rental values, that investment in residential property development will in the next three years continue to enjoy and maintain an upward growth rate. Again, some of the tenants were not satisfied with the drainage system and waste disposal facilities in their areas, hence there is need for property developers to provide and improve on the quality of the infrastructure.

The findings of this study show that the impact of locational characteristics on housing condition is significant. The impact of apartment characteristics such as the number of bedrooms, the availability of amenities (water and electricity supply), availability of facilities (toilet and bathroom) is statistically significant in determining rental charges. Sharing of apartment facilities also has a significant impact on the housing conditions. This agrees with Ankeli *et al.*, [24-27] and Bhada and Dan, [28].

5. Conclusion

The type of housing people live in is an indication of the level of their income, preference, taste as well as wealth, and prestige, and the availability of facilities have implications for health and the environment. Concerns about sanitation arise with the challenge of refuse management in growing cities. Housing needs in Benin City, Edo State are critical in determining the welfare of tenants. The study also concludes that developers should ensure that all basic infrastructural facilities that will attract higher values to their property be provided. This in line with several studies [24-27, 29-30]. Government should make implementable policies and established housing quality standards and supervisory agencies that will be responsible for the monitoring of housing standards. Government should make policies aimed at defining environmental and housing quality standards and provide supervisory agencies that will be responsible for the monitoring and implementation of housing standards.

6. Recommendations

It is recommended that the need for property owners/developers and users to be educated on the need for the provision of basic facilities and sustainable maintenance culture.

However, the study recommends that the overall quality of the existing housing stock and environment could be improved through government intervention in the form of compulsory rehabilitation and urban renewal programs. This will invariably improve the quality of life of residents in the study area.

Also, a periodical review of the master plan of the study area is advocated. Reviews of master plans are necessary to monitor the growth of towns and cities, thereby control spontaneous developments that are

detrimental to the well-being of residents and the estates. This should be implemented to update and regularize changes in the master plan to incorporate uses that are hitherto absent in the plan due to their significances.

References

- [1]. Jiboye, A. D. (2013). The challenges of sustainable housing and urban development in Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Research and Policies*. 4(3), 23-27.
- [2]. Dabara, I.D., Okorie, A., Ankel, I. A & Alabi, J.K. (2012). Evaluation of the relationships between urban infrastructure and flood disaster in Gombe metropolis. *Journal of Sustainable Development* 5(7), 137-148. Available online at <http://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/jsd/article/view/16924>.
- [3]. Bello, I. K, Adeniji, W & Arowosegbe, O. S. (2013): The effects of urban infrastructural development on property value merit. *Research Journal of Art, Social Science and Humanities* (ISSN: 2350-2258).
- [4]. Fernandez-Duran, L., Llorca, A., Ruiz, N., Valero, S & Botti, V. (2011). The impact of location on housing prices; Applying the artificial neural network model as an analytical tool. Ersas conference paper No. 11, p. 1595. European regional science association.
- [5]. Odimegwu, C., & Somefun, O. D. (2017). Ethnicity, gender and risky sexual behaviour among Nigerian youth: an alternative explanation. *Reproductive health*, 14(1), 1-15.
- [6]. Taub, Ben. (2017). "The desperate journey of a trafficked girl". *The New Yorker*. Archived from the original on 3 April 2017. In 1897, after the Edo slaughtered a British delegation, colonial forces, pledging to end slavery and ritual sacrifice, ransacked the city and burned it to the ground.
- [7]. Koutonin, Mawuna. (2016). "Story of cities 5: Benin City, the mighty medieval capital now lost without trace". Retrieved 2 April 2018.
- [8]. Toyin, Falola. (2005). Akinwunmi, Ogundiran (ed.). *Precolonial Nigeria* (2005 ed.). African World Press Inc. pp. 264–265. ISBN 978-1592212194.
- [9]. Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage English Language Teaching; Vol. 12, No. 5. ISSN 1916-4742 E-ISSN 1916-4750. Published by Canadian Center of Science and Education.
- [10]. UN-Habitat. (2006). *Regulatory framework and strategic urban planning and management*, A paper presented at the African ministerial conference on housing and urban development in Nairobi, April 3 – 4, 2006. Retrieved from: <http://www.unhabitat.org>.
- [11]. Ukabam, T. A. (2008). The relationship between housing quality and residential property values in Yaba and Ebute-Metta, Lagos. *The Yaba Journal of Environmental Studies*, 2(1):32-37.
- [12]. Yoade, A.O., Olayiwola, L. M & Popoola, K.O. (2013). Socio-cultural challenges to urban renewal in Ile-Ife, Nigeria; *Online Journal of African Affairs*; 2(1): 10-18.
- [13]. Yoade, A.O and Adeyemi, O.O. (2015). Influence of inner-city decay on residents "health in Ile-Ife, Nigeria; *Journal of Environment and Earth Science*, 5(18): 137-145.
- [14]. Yust, M. M., Pedroche, J., Megías, C., Girón-Calle, J., Alaiz, M., Millán, F & Vioque, J. (2017). Improvement of protein extraction from sunflower meal by hydrolysis with alcalase. *Instituto de la Grasa, CSIC. Avenida Padre García Tejero 4. 41012-Sevilla, Spain. E-mail: jvioque@cica.es*.
- [15]. Olujimi, J. A. B and Bello, M. O. (2009). Effects of Infrastructural Facilities on the Rental Values of Residential Property. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(4), 332-341.
- [16]. Olujimi, J.A.B. (2010). Analysis of the Relationships of infrastructural facilities in the determination of rental values of residential properties in Akure, Nigeria. *Arts and Social Sciences Journal*.
- [17]. Kiel, K. A and Zabel, J. E. (2008). Location, location, location: The 3I approach to house price determination. *Journal of Housing Economics* 17(2): 175-190.
- [18]. Ilesanmi, S. O., Ige, O. K & Adebisi, A.O. (2012). The managed hypertensive: The costs of blood pressure control in a Nigerian town. *Pan Afr Med J*. 12:96.
- [19]. Mbachu, J. I and Lenono, N. (2005). Factors influencing market values of residential properties. Paper presented at the Queensland University of Technology research week international conference, Brisbane, Australia. 4-8 July.

- [20]. Morris, A. S., Criss, M. M., Silk, J. S and Houlberg, B. J. (2017). The impact of parenting on emotion regulation during childhood and adolescence. *Child Development Perspectives*, 11(4), 233–238. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdep.12238>.
- [21]. Egbenta, R. I. (2001). Application of regression analysis to property valuation, being a critical analysis/thesis submitted to national council of the Nigerian institution of estate surveyors and valuers in fulfillment of the test of professional competence in to corporate membership of the institution.
- [22]. Everett, T. C., Morgan, P. J & Brydges, R. (2017). The impact of critical event checklists on medical management and teamwork during simulated crises in a surgical daycare facility. *anaesthesia*; 350-8.
- [23]. Chukwuma, C. Nwuba and Salawu, B. M. (2010). Planned and integrated approach to maintenance of urban infrastructure in Nigeria. *Environ-Tech is a Journal of the College of Environmental Studies, kaduna polytechnic, kaduna, Nigeria*. Published in Environ-Tech Vol. 1 No 1.
- [24]. Ankeli, I.A., Dabara, I.D., Oyeleke, O.O., Guyimu, J & Oladimeji, E.J. (2015a). Infrastructure financing and urban development in Nigeria. *Conference of the International Journal of Arts & Sciences*, CD-ROM. ISSN: 1943-6114: 08(01):79–86
- [25]. Ankeli, A.I, Dabara, D.I, Oyeleke O. O, Guyimu, J & Oladimeji, E.J. (2015b). Housing condition and residential property rental values in Ede Nigeria. *Conference of the International Journal of Arts & Sciences*, CD-ROM. ISSN: 1943-6114: 08(01):53–61.
- [26]. Ankeli, P. I. (2015). Seroprevalence, isolation and molecular identification of mycoplasma mycoides subsp. mycoides from cattle in plateau state, Nigeria. MSc thesis, ahmadubello university, zaria, Nigeria.
- [27]. Ankeli, P. I., Raji, M. A., Kazeem, H. M., Tambuwal, F. M., Francis, M. I., Ikpa, L. T., Fagbamila, I. O., Luka, P. D & Nwankpa, N. D. (2017). Seroprevalence of contagious bovine pleuropneumoniain plateau state, north-central Nigeria. *Bull. Anim. Hlth. Prod. Africa*. 65(2): 357-366.
- [28]. Bhada, Perinaz and Hoornweg, Dan. (2009). The global city indicators program: A more credible voice for cities. Directions in urban development. World Bank, Washington, DC. © World Bank. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/10244> License: CC BY 3.0 IGO.
- [29]. Agbola, T and Adegoke, S.A.(2007). Economics in housing. In tundeagbola, layiegunjobi & C.O. olatubara (eds.), *Housing Development and Management*. A book of readings (pp.), department of urban and regional planning, faculty of social sciences, university of Ibadan, Nigeria.
- [30]. Aluko, O. (2011). The effects of location and neighborhood attributes on housing values in metropolitan Lagos. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management*, 4(2):69-82.

